

1 **Supplementary Materials**

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3 **Diet outweighs genetics in shaping gut microbiomes in Asian honeybee**

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20 **Fig. S1. Community composition and diversity at the phylotype level in gut**
 21 **microbiota from *A. cerana*.** The results were analyzed by Kraken2 with 390 bee gut
 22 bacteria genomes as reference in Supplementary Table 2. Host populations are indicated
 23 by short bars at the top.

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27 **Fig. S2.** The relative abundance of core bacteria with the *de novo* methods were
28 highly correlated with the results from reference-based Kraken2 methods.

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32 **Fig. S3.** Maximal-likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of *Gilliamella* strains from
33 bees. ML tree was built on the core genes existing in all strain genomes. Branch colors
34 correspond to host species.

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37 **Fig. S4. Maximal-likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of *Snodgrassella* strains from**
 38 **bees. ML tree was built on the core genes existing in all strain genomes. Branch colors**
 39 **correspond to host species.**

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43 **Fig. S5. Maximal-likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of *Lactobacillus* strains from**
 44 **bees.** ML tree was built on the core genes existing in all strain genomes. Branch colors
 45 correspond to host species.
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 49 **Fig. S6. Maximal-likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of *Bifidobacterium* strains**
 50 **from bees.** ML tree was built on the core genes existing in all strain genomes. Branch
 51 colors correspond to host species.

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56 **Fig. S7.** The SDP composition of *Lactobacillus* Firm-4 in gut metagenome samples
 57 of *A. cerana* estimated by MIDAS.

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61 **Fig. S8.** PCoA of *Gilliamella* SDP composition in populations of *A. cerana*.

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64 **Fig. S9. Fraction of SNVs for the dominant SDPs varied in populations of *A. cerana*.**

65 Dominant SDPs include those show relatively high frequency in all samples. SNVs in

66 each sample were calculated from all SNPs existing in each SDP.

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Fig. S10. SNV differences for dominant SDPs in the gut microbiome from 15 populations of *A. cerana*.

Fig. S11. The pollen composition at the family level varied in honey from populations of *A. cerana*.

Fig. S12. SNP heritability of the core phylotypes and SDPs for gut microbiota in *A. cerana*. Each point represents the estimated PVE with GEMMA by genome-wide SNPs for the abundance of the core phylotypes and SDPs. Bars indicate SE measurements around the estimate. PVE: Percentage of Variance Explained.

Fig. S13. Distribution of KEGG orthologs (KOs) in gut microbes from 15 populations of *A. cerana*. Horizontal bars on the bottom left represent KO numbers annotated in each population. Vertical bars indicate the numbers of KOs exclusively associated with one or multiple groups. The common KO numbers in each category are in red. The area of each KO category is proportional to the KO number.

Fig. S14. Gut microbe KO abundance showed significant difference among populations with PCoA.

Fig. S16. Glycoside hydrolases (GH) and polysaccharide lyases (PL) gene profiles in gut microbiota from populations of *A. cerana*. Color represents the frequency of the GH/PL family in each population.

Fig. S17. Gut microbe community composition showed significant difference between *A. cerana* and *A. mellifera* with PCoA. (A) Gut microbe community difference at the host species level. (B) Gut microbe community composition showed variation among different populations of *A. cerana* (including population from Japan) with PCoA.

Fig. S18. Gene cluster numbers in gut microbiota varies in *A. cerana* and *A. mellifera*. All comparisons were based on the 400Mb bacteria-mapped reads. (A) Gene cluster numbers per sample showed difference in different populations of *A. cerana* and *A. mellifera*. (B) Cumulative number for gene cluster numbers in gut metagenome from *A. mellifera* and each population of *A. cerana*.